

THE INTERRELATIONSHIP IN THE PSYCHE OF THE EDUCATOR AND THE LEARNER

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6564881>

Ismatova Nargiza Ikramovna

Lecturer at the Karshi institute of engineering and economics

Annotation: *The article is aimed at increasing the intellectual potential of students in the educational process and the processes related to the development of human mental activity and the psyche of students, conscious understanding of the content of the educational process, intellectual development of students, improving existing skills, effective socialization, consistent work on themselves. , in the pursuit of professional maturity and the pursuit of theoretical ideas of creativity, humanism, the study of the growing interest of students in education, professional development in the presence of similar information.*

Key words: *education, student, upbringing, information, content, essence, activity, process, result.*

The rapid penetration of innovations into the education system in our country, the determination of global information in modern conditions, encourages every student to have a large amount of information. Today's young people need to be educated in the conditions of similar information in their personal development, intellectual development, development of existing abilities, effective socialization, consistent work on themselves, professional development and the pursuit of theoretical ideas of creativity, humanism. promotes an increase in interest in perfection.

The educational process includes the components of the educational process, including teaching and the tools used, methods of teaching to solve specific goals and objectives, the participation of independent learners and educators in this process, as well as visual and technical aids [1].

The educational process, the continuity and continuity between the teacher and the learner, that is, the connection is an important component of the pedagogical process. At the same time it is always necessary to pay attention to the following ideas of the reading process:

- Reading is a direct process through which learners receive new information throughout their lives;

- There is a lack of teaching children to read, they need to be taught to read thoughtfully, and as a result, students will have a new idea and will be able to enter the scientific community;
- Reading is not just a science of learning, but a tool for thinking and knowing the world;
- Reading and response to reading is a key way of critical analysis;
- The study of different subjects usually requires a lot of independent reading from the learner, so understanding the reading process can improve the mastery and analysis of what is read in a particular subject [2, 3, 4].

This means that the state of the learner in the educational process will also be a solid didactic basis for achieving optimal options for activities in this area. In this regard, the intellectual potential, mental and physiological health of the learner and their sense of joy are very important in the educational process.

“A student's sense of joy is an important spiritual product in creating a successful environment for them to complete learning tasks in the classroom.

This is one of the main aspects of the educational process, in which one of the most effective ways to stimulate the desire to read is realized, and in them a sense of joy is realized.

It is well known that a learner cannot fully believe in subsequent successes unless he or she experiences the joys of success. Therefore, experienced teachers choose tasks for learners in such a way that they become easy tasks to solve at the appropriate stage. It uses two types of tasks, one of which is easily completed by the learner, and creates an aspiration base to solve another relatively more complex task. The success base is created by stratifying tasks of the same complexity. Choosing a comfortable spiritual environment to complete the learning tasks plays an important role in creating a situation of success. A comfortable micro-social environment eliminates feelings of mutual insecurity, fear or apprehension while reading. In this case, the state of hesitation is replaced by a state of confidence [5, 6].

The technology of educational play activities is also important in ensuring the connection between the educational process and its participants. Such technology is more similar to stratified learning technology, in that the learning game becomes meaningful when the educator and learner interact. To do this, the project of the training game should be developed in advance and the assessment of the planned results should be determined in advance, as well as the training tasks should be

clearly defined, methodological methods and possibilities of overcoming a complex situation should be identified.

When conducting educational work in order to organize the learning activities of learners, the educator must not forget that he must first solve three tasks through the learning process, that is, three goals through teaching. These goals combine the activities of educators and learners.

1. The educational purpose is to know the content of educational materials, that is, to be able to master and apply scientific knowledge related to this subject.

2. The educational goal is to form one's own personal qualities, beliefs under the influence of the ideas and worldviews that lie in its content by mastering the basics of science.

3. The developmental goal is to develop a person's mental maturity, cognitive abilities, attitude to study, work under the influence of the educational process [7, 8, 9].

As a result of achieving these goals, the learner develops the ability to work independently, teaches him to think, thinking dominates the learning process.

Modernity in education - the idea of a national program is the obligation to introduce scientifically based and tested didactic innovations, active methods and forms, procedures in educational practice. The level of development of education is characterized by scientific and technical innovations included in its content.

The development of the intellectual sphere in education is the process of developing students' thinking (knowledge, creativity), memory, attention, mental qualities (depth, flexibility, thrift, independence), thinking skills, learning skills, subject knowledge, learning and skills.

Development of willpower in education is a process of formation of goal-orientation in the learner, in which to overcome the tension of nerves and muscles, initiative, self-confidence, self-management, knowledge (how to operate), activity development, how to implement it and external control. skills such as incompetence are important.

The development of the motivational sphere in education is the process of shaping the learner's needs for intellectual knowledge, understanding of nature, society, human thinking and the laws of cognition.

The development of the emotional sphere in education is a process of developing in the learner the necessary skills to manage their emotions and mental states, in which it is important to cultivate the ability to overcome excessive anxiety and self-assessment.

In general, the educational process consists of 4 main stages:

1. Understand the material to be mastered.
2. The formation of the concept of choosing it.
3. Development of skills and competencies to strengthen and improve knowledge.
4. Apply the acquired skills and abilities in practice.

Each stage is characterized by a specific description of the learners' cognitive activity. This activity requires special guidance from the educator [10].

The essence of the knowledge acquired at the initial stage of the learning process is understood using the methods of analysis and synthesis.

Analysis (breaking into pieces) - is the division of things, events and happenings into components, pieces. For example, pomegranate is divided into hard skin, layers - layers and grains.

Synthesis is the process of thinking that is the opposite of analysis. What is being studied in it is the unification of the individual parts of events and happenings as a whole.

Learners' thinking activities are also reflected in comparisons.

Comparison is an operation of thinking aimed at finding differences and similarities, equality and inequality in things and events.

Inductive and deductive thinking are important in understanding the learning material.

Inductive reasoning (inference) is a method of logical cognition, one of the forms of thinking, based on inference, which goes from the individual or individual cases to the general, from some facts to generalizations.

Deductive inference (division, inference) is a method of drawing logical conclusions from general judgments to specific judgments, one of the forms of thinking.

Concepts are formed in learners based on the use of methods of analysis, synthesis, comparison, inductive reasoning and deductive reasoning.

Concept is a form of thinking in which the object of reality is the expression of important signs and features of events in a single word or combination of words. As the learning process takes on a dialectical character, the concepts gradually deepen and become more complex.

The assimilation of information, the formation of concepts, the assimilation of knowledge is an important situation in the overall process. The inability to reflect on the material studied, the inability to be independent in

its educational and labor activities, and the lack of a creative approach to them lead to the superficial assimilation of knowledge.

We believe that the structural structure, which allows us to study the legal relationship between the educational process and social systems and conditions, is the leading methodological resource, the basis for us to study the laws of education. Then the relationship between teaching and learning processes, which are part of education, and, finally, the tasks and content of the learning process are considered.

The components of the educational process are: purposefulness, motivational - explanatory, content, operational activities (methods, forms of education), control, correction, assessment, outcome assessment. The components of the educational process reflect the development of interactions between educators and learners, from goal setting to setting goals and achieving tangible results. At the same time, these components of the educational process should take into account the established periodic cooperation of educators and learners.

In conclusion, effective ways of implementing the educational process are achieved through an integral link between the educator and the learner. For this reason, feedback in the learning process and its management is a key tool for learners to understand the learning material. Here, feedback is extremely important in ensuring that the educator and learner are moving towards the intended goal and adjusting the process as needed. It guarantees the selection of the optimal option to achieve the planned goal. Through this, learners understand the essence of the learning material, find optimal solutions, ideas and laws known in pedagogical practice, as well as learners improve their intellectual potential.

REFERENCES:

1. Қўйсинов О.А., Шарипов Ш.С., Арипов М., Бегимқулов У. ва.б. Билим олишнинг интеллектуал тизимини ишлаб чиқиш назарияси ва амалиёти. Монография. Т.: “Фан”, 2011. Б. 14.
2. Маслоу А.Г. Мотивация и личность. СПб. : Питер. 2016. С. 290.
3. Муслимов Н.А., Рахимов З.Т., Хўжаев А.А. Касбий педагогика. Дарслик. Тошкент “Ворис” нашриёти – 2020. Б. 517.
4. Муслимов Н.А., Рахимов З.Т., Хўжаев А.А., Қодиров Ҳ.Ш. Таълим технологиялари. Дарслик. Тошкент “Ворис” нашриёти – 2019. Б. 568.

5. Рахимов З.Т. Талабалар ўқув-билиш фаолиятини ривожлантиришга инновацион ёндашув. Тошкент давлат педагогика университети Илмий ахборотлари. Илмий-назарий журнали, 3-сон (19) 2019. Б. 92-97.

6. Рахимов З.Т., Муслимов Ш.Н., Имомов М.П., Келдиёрова М.Ф. Педагогик технологиялар // Ўқув қўлланма. Тошкент: «Фан ва технологиялар нашриёт-матбаа уйи», 2021. Б. 192.

7. Турдиев Ш.Р., Келдиёрова М.Ф. Таълим жараёнини тизимли ёндашув асосида педагогик технологиялардан фойдаланган ҳолда ташкил этиш // Замоновий таълим. Илмий-амалий оммабоп журнал. – Тошкент, 2019. – № 12. Б. 31-36.

8. Турдиев Ш.Р., Келдиёрова М.Ф. Организация в процессе обучения учебно исследовательской работы студентов. Научно-методический журнал “Вестник науки и образования” Издательство «Проблемы науки» 2020. № 5 (83). Часть 2. С. 21-25.

9. Турдиев Ш.Р., Келдиёрова М.Ф. Личные и профессиональные особенности учителя. Научно-методический журнал “Проблемы современной науки и образования” 2020. № 6 (151). Часть 1. С. 67-72.

10. Шадиев Р.Д., Келдиёрова М.Ф. Системный подход как важный фактор организации образовательного процесса. Научно-методический журнал “Проблемы педагогики” № 6 (51), 2020. С. 6-9.